

Impediments in Language Teachings: Breaking the Language Barriers

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Abstract:-

Learning a foreign language at different levels of proficiency involves the acquisition of a great numbers of words, learning, reading and speaking. The paper throws mainly light on impediments or obstacles a teacher or a learner face. In this paper, problems in vocabulary, learning, speaking are elaborated on and tried to give some practical guidelines to ameliorate them. The paper offers some language learning strategies to make ELT easier and interesting. It gives some introduction of technology, Apps and devices which are really helpful. The purpose of this study is to give practically implemented strategies and ideas which writer has said.

Keywords:- Vocabulary; Memory; Impediments; Obstacles; Language

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The article is about the challenges or impediment faced by language learners and teachers of language. Learning a foreign language with proficiency involves many things such as speaking, reading, vocabulary

and Grammar. So, there can be obstacles or impediments in many stages as learning, Reading, writing and selection of appropriate words. Generally in second language students and teacher face problems of selection of vocabulary also. Students want to express in front of teacher but unable to as they lack exact words even. What teachers face in this part is, how to tell them words. As their help make them dependant too. We all know that English has provided opportunities for all to express and think in every field possible. It is lingua franca of the world and one feel comfortable when fluent in it communication all over the globe can only be possible just because of flawless knowledge of English chances of Employment also increase to the fullest if one is well versed in English the main problem we teachers feel in teaching is lack of four elements in teaching as phonology, morphology, semantic and syntax. This is the greatest hurdle which make student's ability lesser.

Reasons behind Non-proficiency in second Language:

- English, as we all know is not a completely phonetical language. We lack proper models of teaching. The IPA charts are not introduced at school level. Students do not know the proper sounds of Alphabets. So, they can't even pronounce. I visited Oxford University in July 2014 to attend summer school. There I met and learn pronunciation skills from Adrian Underhill, the man behind pronchart by Macmillan, and then I come to know that basically our students are completely unaware of sounds

Alphabets and their combination produced.

- Some or Every language has different rules, sounds and spellings. Our Mother Tongue is entirely different. There is no correlation. So, Teachers have to work a Gardener or a pot pitcher. Who work according to situation to soil-the seeds or making the pots. Speaking is a great hurdle that too speaking fluently. Speaking defects make students hesitant of expressing and they avoid teacher and their lectures. There are many reasons for it such as family background, lack of learning and reading skills, social pressure, teacher's non-cooperative behaviour etc. Some students suffer from physical problems also such as cleft palate, improper teeth alignment and some or other psychological and neurological problems.
- Learning problems also cause hurdles. It is improper knowledge, lack of fluency, insufficient knowledge of words, lack of confidence and interest also cause problems. A teacher can teach patiently but students have to learn by themselves.
- Lack of vocabulary is also a great hurdle conventional method of increasing vocabulary such as use of flash cards, use of Dictionaries (bilingual and monolingual both), making notebooks increase short term memory of vocabulary but we have to change them for better. My stay at Oxford makes me aware that they use long term policies for language learning.

I believe that cultivating caring, engaged relationships with students and their families will help students to feel connected to their college and, hopefully, enhance their feelings about college and their self-esteem. I would like to be remembered as a teacher that cared, one that made a difference in their lives. The role that a teacher plays in the lives of students and

the teacher's potential to improve the quality of life for students cannot be underestimated. I still remember my first year in my college, when I was teaching with my highest enthusiasm level and always notice one of my most punctual students, coming daily, sitting on first row first seat, listening carefully and attentively but leaving the classroom in a confused state of mind. On one fine day, I asked everyone, and then she broke down. She was in a habit of understanding English with the help of her mother tongue. I promised her to help but for some time. Later with proper guidance she overcomes this habit and to my proud, she is also a secondary level teacher now in one of Public School. So, the situation varies time to time and year by year and a good teacher has to take decision as per the situation and need of the hour. Our main aim is to make students well versed not let them down of their inabilities.

A language can never be taught but we have to catch language. From childhood, we have been taught that imitation plays a leading and significant role in language learning and teaching. So, the duty of teachers of language increases more than other subjects. They have to set models and perfect lessons for their students. They have to set different targets and goals for their students. In the era of technology, we can take help of gadgets and electronic appliances to promote students. Easier computers were introduced in our curriculum for better teaching and understanding. Now, we have many other devices such as Android Phones, Ipad's, and Laptops, which offer many modern useful teaching aids. Now a days not only use of Internet but many Apps are there to help students to gain perfection in teaching and learning.

“The English language is nobody's special property. It is the property of the

imagination: it is the property of the language itself.”

~Derek Walcott

Suggestions to learn and Teach English:-

- Institutions should establish language labs for belts teaching and understanding.
- Teachers should give personal attention for every student's problems.
- Institutions should take help and consultation of some good speech Therapist.
- More conversational opportunities in classroom will help.
- Tongue Twister exercises, use of Sudoku type puzzles will also help.
- IPA sounds, stress, unstressed syllabus tone and pronchart should be introduced at easily level to understand every nook and corner of language.
- Communication exercises, speech and speaking assignments will help a lot.
- Language teachers have to take help of some therapist and linguist also to make their teaching more students friendly and easy to understand.

Conclusion:

Students with English as a second language (ESL) constitute a significant percentage of the population of our schools and colleges in our country. This population continues to increase more rapidly than that of native English speaking students. This presents a unique challenge for teachers as we strive to help these students achieve in learning the English language and the academic material specified in our content area learning standards. This paper is a summary and critical analysis of problems and challenges ELT face. The article focuses on the challenges students face and how they communicate with teachers. The English that students are taught is academic English. They often lack the ability to interact in social settings with English speaking peers because they are in separate classrooms and

often have limited opportunity to interact academically or socially. They often have great difficulty learning the "slang" and social English because they have no one to learn it from. Another problem is difference of culture and traditions. It refers to the way language and cultures are related and the amount of cultural knowledge required comprehending meaning or participating in an activity. Meanings of words are determined by the uses of words within linguistic and cultural settings, never the same in any two cultures. English learners need to learn the words in English as well as the cultural background that gives the words their English meaning. They need to learn words in context to understand the meaning. The next barrier refers to the number of unfamiliar words encountered as an English learner reads a text or listens to teacher or peer academic talk. Teachers can lighten this load by rewriting or explaining text material in the way students want or accept. Our main aim should be teaching English in its correct way not to produce it as a hard nut to crack.

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